

RSS Channel-Based Integration for BLE Fingerprinting Positioning

2023 Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)

Zenodo package documentation

Abstract

This document contains the description of the supporting material of the work entitled "RSS Channel-Based Integration for BLE Fingerprinting Positioning" and presented in the "2023 Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation conference (IPIN 2023)" published in the Zenodo repository.

1 Introduction

Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) technology has gained widespread popularity in recent years due to its low power consumption and broad applicability in various domains, including indoor positioning. Among the different approaches to indoor positioning, fingerprinting has emerged as a promising technique. Fingerprinting involves creating a database of signal measurements at known locations (reference points) and then using this database to estimate the position of a device based on its current signal measurements.

One of the key challenges in BLE-based fingerprinting is the variability of Received Signal Strength (RSS) measurements. RSS values can fluctuate significantly due to multipath effects, interference, and the utilization of different frequency channels within the BLE spectrum. This variability can degrade the accuracy of positioning systems.

In this study, we aim to address this challenge by incorporating frequency information into the positioning process. By leveraging the frequency channels on which RSS measurements are taken, we propose methods to improve positioning accuracy. We evaluate our approaches using two distinct BLE RSS databases, one of which was specifically developed for this research. The results show that frequency information can significantly enhance positioning accuracy, highlighting the importance of considering this factor in BLE-based positioning systems.

2 Experimental Setup

The positioning environment consisted of a section in a university building comprising three different regions. The first region is divided into a walkway and an inner courtyard. The second is a larger walkway of approximately $3 \times 2 \text{ m}^2$ that connects the first zone with the last region, which is a 20 m long corridor with offices on both sides. Over the environment, five different C211 uBlox beacons were placed and configured to transmit a BLE signal every 20 ms with a transmission power of 0 dBm. In each region, a different size grid was used to select the Reference Points (RPs). Figure 1 (right) shows the floor map with the three regions, beacon locations, reference points, and test points positions.

Since channel information is not available in most off-the-shelf devices, the uBlox AoA C211 antennas and C209 tags were used. These modules work with BLE 5.1 and incorporate an array of antennas to compute the angle-of-arrival (AoA). However, they were used in this work since they allowed us to associate each received BLE signal with its transmission frequency. The uBlox C211 antenna was attached to the Pioneer 3-DX robot shown Figure 1 (left), which is a small two-wheel robot controlled by a Raspberry Pi 3 Model B. Information from the antenna was transferred to the Raspberry Pi board using a USB cable. The board was in constant communication via Wi-Fi with a laptop running Matlab that acted as a server to store and process data.

The data collection process involved both static and dynamic measurements. Static measurements were taken at predetermined reference points within the grid, where the robot remained stationary. Dynamic measurements involved the robot moving along predefined paths within the environment. Both types of measurements were repeated multiple times to ensure variability and robustness in the dataset.

Figure 1: Pioneer 3-DX robot and uBlox antenna used for data collection (left). Positioning area with the reference points and beacon positions (right).

3 Database Description

The UEx URI 2023 Dataset comprises BLE RSS measurements collected in a university building, encompassing three distinct regions. The dataset is structured in a single CSV file with multiple columns, each containing different types of information:

- **rss**: Received Signal Strength values in dBm as provided by the uBlox antennas.
- **azimuth**: Angle of arrival (azimuth) provided by the uBlox antenna, measured in degrees (not used in the article).
- **elevation**: Angle of arrival (elevation) provided by the uBlox antenna, measured in degrees.
- **timestamps**: Measurement timestamps provided by the antenna, measured in milliseconds with respect to antenna boot.
- **deviceId**: ID code of the transmitter (several transmitters were used, while only one receiver was used).
- **channel**: Frequency channel (37, 38, or 39) in which the RSS was measured.
- **coordinate**: Measurement coordinates corresponding to the RSS value.
- **type**: 1 for static training, 2 for dynamic training, 3 for static test, and 4 for dynamic test. Only types 1 and 3 were used.
- **orientation**: North (1), east (2), south (3), and west (4).
- **campaign**: Collection was divided into several continuous campaigns.

Two MATLAB scripts are included. The first script, `LOAD_DATA`, loads the data from the provided database, reads the CSV files, creates the database in MATLAB format, and converts them into fingerprinting matrices using the strategies proposed in the article. The second script, `LOAD_EXTERNAL`, processes the secondary database by selecting measurements associated with channels 37, 38, and 39, saving them in a format similar to that used for our primary database.